

MAKING RESEARCH RESULTS WORK FOR SOCIETY

Commission Recommendation on Code of practice on standardisation

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ERA Action 7: Upgrade EU guidance for better knowledge valorisation

Develop and endorse Guiding principles for knowledge valorisation

Respond to the needs and feedback of knowledge valorisation actors including policy making and provide a common reference to improve knowledge valorisation in the EU.

Council Recommendation (EU) 2022/2415 adopted on 2 December 2022

i) Create a Code of practice on the management of intellectual assets

Co-create hands-on guidance with and for R&I actors on how to handle challenges related to intellectual asset management in the current R&I ecosystem.

Commission Recommendation adopted on 1 March 2023

ii) Create a Code of practice on standardisation

Co-create hands-on guidance with and for R&I actors on how to valorise project results through standardisation.

Commission Recommendation adopted on 1 March 2023

Standardisation Strategy – the key actions

No alignment with political priorities

- Enhance Annual WP to reflect standardisation urgencies
- High-Level Forum to assist in prioritisation
- Review of all harmonised European standards against contribution to zero-emission economy and Europe's Digital Decade
- EU excellence hub and Chief Standardisation Officer

Good governance concerns

- Proposal for amendment → introducing good governance principles for ESOs
- Call to ESOs to modernise their governance
- Announce the Evaluation of Regulation 1025/2012
- MS peer review process on SME-friendly conditions

Geopolitics of standards

- Coordination of EU MS/NSB positions
- International standards for a free, open and secure global internet
- EU funding (Horizon, NICI), pilots in African countries and EU Neighbourhood
- Continuation of concerted actions with like-minded partners (TTC, Japan)

Unexploited potential of pre-normative work

- Code of Practice for researchers
- Standardisation Booster

Lack of experts

- Targeted actions on education and skills:
 - Horizon Europe/COST
 - EU Academy Platform/e-learning material
 - Standardisation University Days

Objective of the code of practice on standardisation

Supporting our stakeholders to valorise their R&I results through standardisation by

- Contributing to the synchronisation and systemic integration of R&I and standardisation
- Providing guidance to researchers and innovators

Process for establishing the Code

- Survey with beneficiaries – May-June 2021
- Scoping study – June 2021-March 2022
- Publication of the first draft of the Code – 19 May 2022
- Stakeholder consultation – May – June 2022
- Code published 1 March 2023

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/94a9bba7-a43b-11ec-83e1-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-253037686>

Recommendations addressed at 3 main stakeholder groups

Based on the lessons learnt and success factors from examples of Horizon 2020 projects

Higher education
institutions and
research & innovation
organisations

Project partners

Policy and
stakeholders

Inclusiveness – all types of projects with a wide range of TRLs

Higher education institutions and research and innovation organisations

- Developing a standardisation policy, self-standing or as part of an IP or research results valorisation policy
- Considering standardisation activities in the career development plans
- Providing for education and training on standardisation
- Making Technology Transfer Offices fit for standardisation
- Developing an indicator and evaluation system

Project partners

- Analyses of the landscape
- Common understanding and strategic position on standardisation
- Involving partners with expertise in making standardisation a tangible part of the project
- Investing in stakeholder engagement
- Realistic outputs, outcomes and impacts and combined qualitative and quantitative reporting
- Ensuring sustainability beyond the project duration

Policy and stakeholders

- Promoting by Member States standardisation as means of knowledge valorisation
- Examining by Member States the standardisation needs of startups and SMEs in R&I projects
- Standards Development Organisation to develop their service portfolios to align with R&I activities
- Use by Member States national support in relation to standardisation as a R&I valorisation tool

More information

- Find out more information about the Code of practice:
 - [Guiding Principles for Knowledge Valorisation implementing Codes of Practice \(europa.eu\)](#)
 - [Commission adopts Recommendations on codes of practice for the management of intellectual asset and standardisation \(europa.eu\)](#)
 - [Factsheet: Code of practice on standardisation in the European Research Area - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

Thank you

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